

Review of Research

International Online Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: 2249-894X

Impact Factor : 3.1402(UIF)

Volume - 5 | Issue - 5 | Feb - 2016

“A STUDY OF WEB PORTAL FEATURES AS A KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN SCHOOL EDUCATION.”

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ABSTRACT :

The development of Web has affected different aspects of our lives, such as communication, sharing knowledge, searching for jobs, social activities, etc. The web portal as a gateway in the World Wide Web is a starting point for people who are connecting to the Internet. The web portal as the type of knowledge management system provides a rich space to share and search information as well as communication services like free email or content provision for the users. This research aims to

discover the university needs to the web portal as a necessary tool for students in the schools to help them in getting the required information. A survey was conducted to gather students' requirements which can be incorporated in to portal to be developed.

KEYWORDS : *Knowledge, Knowledge management system, Knowledge sharing, webportal.*

INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in the field of available ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) resources have led to a renewed interest of learners in knowledge acquisition through various means. It makes students better prepared, better skilled and more informed in comparison to their earlier counterparts.

For any Educational institution knowledge management (KM) plays pivotal role, in race for cut throat competition among other runners.

Among leading school institutions, knowledge management has become prime requisite. Information dissemination in education has seen an enormous flow because of Internet. Website of schools has been essential requirement to stand themselves among competitors. Institutions' Website

progressively led to web portal development with better end user reach and interaction features. Web portals become significant as a result of students getting the required information on-line. It is indispensable that schools have a dynamic association with the understudies by sharing the sorted out knowledge by means of the portal and help the understudies from untidy information on the Web. There are different sorts' web portals with different utilities that give advantages to the clients. Every client can have his or her own particular unmistakable meaning of web portals. Essentially, a portal is a passage to online network available resources through the Intranet, extranet or Internet, accordingly a basic site page could change this definition, as could an unpredictable website included of a huge number of site pages. The early portals were extremely basic, offering their individuals a static perspective of substance from a little number of sources. For the most part, a web portal permits the clients to get to information from shifted sources in an incorporated way. Aside from the standard internet searcher, web portals give different administrations, for example, email, news, stock costs, information, and diversion, contingent upon the way of business of the portals host establishments.

Literature Review

Before discussing on web portals as an essential knowledge management system in the schools, this paper starts with some basic definition of knowledge, knowledge management and web portal.

A. Knowledge Definition

As per Webster's Dictionary, knowledge is "the fact or condition of knowing something with familiarity gained through experience or association". A more popular definition of knowledge is "the ideas or understandings which an entity possesses that are used to take effective action to achieve the entity's goal(s). This knowledge is specific to the entity which created it."

An understanding of knowledge requires some grasp of its relationship to information. In recent times, theoretical objections to the concept of truth (e.g. by post-modernists) or to that of reliability (e.g. by positivists) have led to some blurring of the distinction. It also tends to obscure the fact that while it can be extremely easy and quick to transfer information from one place to another, knowledge is sticky: it is often very difficult and slow to transfer knowledge from person to another.

B. Knowledge Management System (KMS)

To have an exact meaning of Knowledge Management System (KMS), it is imperative, first take a look at learning substance. Learning is acquired from data and information. Data is an accumulation of words, numbers, perceptions or facts, which are not significant. Data can be changed over to information when it is placed in a significant structure. At last, learning is acquired from information, which has been approved to be valid. Vance characterized information as data that incorporates significant substance, while learning is characterized as confirmed information. Alavi and Leidner [1] expected that learning is information in the individual personality. It implies that it is subjective information that states realities, systems, ideas, understandings, thoughts, perceptions and judgments.

C. Web Portal

A Web portal or public portal refers to a Web site or service that offers a broad array of resources and services, such as e-mail, forums, search engines, and online shopping malls. The first Web portals were online services, such as AOL, that provided access to the Web, but by now most of the traditional search engines have transformed themselves into Web portals to attract and keep a larger audience.

What a portal does:

- Enables universal login
- Handles both structured and unstructured data
- Facilitates multi-channel consistency
- Facilitates messaging and notification
- Automated tuning: pervasive content can be tuned based on personalization, location, browser, etc.
- Integration to other systems

Key features of portals:

- Security
- Access different data
- Transactions
- Search
- Publish Content
- Personal Content

Web portal is not is not just a Website, intranet, extranet, front end for business application, groupware, knowledge management solution or search engine , in fact it is browser based user interface to all the mentioned components.

Major Functions of Portals

According to the analyst and consulting company Ovum - as described in their study "Enterprise Portals: New Strategies for Information Delivery", 2000 - the ideal portal is based on eight functionality areas:

- search and navigation
- information integration (content management)
- personalization
- notification (push technology)
- task management and workflow
- collaboration and groupware
- integration of applications and business intelligence
- infrastructure functionality

Although most of the functionality is not new, what is new is the idea that the business value of the whole is considerably more than the sum of its parts. Thus, a successful portal does not only consist of either a good collaboration support or a good integration of the information sources. Rather it consists of - just like a successful cooking recipe - a well-integrated mixture of the basic portal functionalities.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the web portals and their vital role as a knowledge management system in the schools. Generally, the web portal provides a gate way to access information as well as search, an analytical and communication center for the target users. It is important for the schools to have emphasis on knowledge sharing for supporting the students to access the required resources and information.

How ever, its houldbe considered it will be difficult for web portal to cover all the information's.

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